

Title: Use case demo on emergency department admission for a supervised classification model approach of urgent patient case prioritization

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INTRODUCTION:

Emergency department visit is the most frequent route for patients to get admitted into hospital. However, not every patient requires an immediate hospital admission and prioritizing urgent patients among these cases has become a real challenge within Canadian health care hospitals.

AIM:

To create a supervised classification model for evaluating the accuracy of forecasting future patient admission prioritization cases (i.e., admitted and non-admitted) to relief service volume and improve quality of patient care within emergency department.

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

A simulation software ARENA was used to simulate emergency department admission datasets using a baseline parameters (i.e., average income, distance, demographics and etc.) that were collected from various studies. Based on simulation, two datasets were created which contain 65,535 records of training sets with an assigned label (i.e., admission flag). Using a training set, a supervised classification model workflow was created from data pre-processing to model evaluation steps. Once the model is trained, it is evaluated based on a confusion matrix. The results were evaluated to calculate how many of predicted outcomes (i.e., admission flag) matched with assigned ground truth label of admission flag for each simulated patient case.

RESULTS:

19,660 patient cases were evaluated on a binary class boosted decision trees model. 433 cases were accurately predicted as true admitted; 18,784 cases were predicted as true non-admitted, false admitted of 233 cases and false non-admitted of 210 cases. Thus, ED classification model were reported with an accuracy of 97.7% and a precision of 67.3%.

CONCLUSIONS:

According to the results of this study, more than half of the emergency department admission cases can be predicted through a model for urgent ED admission required cases. However, acceptable margin of precision on this model is still far from an ideal implementation scenario. This is due to low prevalence of the response variable values (i.e., admit cases was 3.04%) in simulated study.

KEYWORDS:

Classification model; Emergency department; Admission; Case prioritization

BIOGRAPHY:

Taesun Yoo has completed his Masters in Health Informatics from University of Toronto, Canada. He is business intelligence QA analyst at Centre for Addiction and Mental Health, a hospital specialized in mental health services for patients.